

POLICY CONFERENCE

UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND
MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE
25 MARCH 2026, BRUSSELS

BEST PRACTICES AND EPR SCHEMES

Omar Degoli
FederlegnoArredo

ECOREFIBRE POLICY CONFERENCE

Recycling figures for wood waste packaging in italy

Wooden packaging recycling (incl. repair)	
Country	Tons/year
Italy	2.164.246
Spain	1.931.000
Germany	950.150
France	684.917
Poland	392.358
Netherlands	308.039
Belgium	218.141
Ireland	109.298
Portugal	90.096
Sweden	80.667

Recycling wood in panels – EU countries

Waste treatment by type of recovery and disposal, 2022 (% of total treatment)

(1) 2020 value.

Sorted by 'Recovery - Recycling', highest to lowest.

Wood waste in panels – Room to grow

47 million tons of wood waste generated in EU
10 million tons recycled

PB wood raw material usage

MDF/HDF wood raw material usage

Italian best practice ingredient #1

Efficient EPR implementation (Rilegno System)

Synergies with other streams of waste

More than half of managed wood waste does not come from packaging (and it does not count towards recycling targets, but the presence of this infrastructure made of collection platforms and trucks, make it easier to channel also other wood waste towards the recycling plants

Cost efficient:

(Environmental contribution 2026: 10 Euro/Ton)

Source: Rilegno

Italian best practice ingredient #2: Whole cycle companies

Presence of recycling capacity (in wood based panels)

Potential utilization (100% recycled wood) of 3.5 million tons ow waste/year

Complete cycle starts from the raw waste material (with some pretreatment mainly to make transport more efficient) and ends with the finished product

The possibility of having a facility that is only focused on turning waste into raw material for its own production makes room for reserach and development of enhanced techniques to make the better use of the input materials.

400 Rilegno platforms complemented with proprietary ones by the companies to optimize collection

Italian best practice ingredients #3 : a regulation that actually favours recycling

Focus on final products

UNI 11951 allows companies to deal with different waste streams, establishing a chain of controls that secure the quality,, without impeding the use of several waste wood stream but focusing on the quality of the final product.

This framework allows companies to invest in improvements on the cleaning, and treatment of the waste wood, and on the technical aspects of production process, in order to be able to use 100% waste wood for production

NORMA ITALIANA

UNI 11951

LUGLIO 2024

Gestione del legno di recupero per la produzione di pannelli a base di legno

Management of recycled wood for the production of wood-based panels

EPR SYSTEMS IN EU (furniture and mattresses)

Already established

Country	Organization	Scope
France	Ecomaison	Furniture Mattresses Construction products Toys DIY
Belgium	Valumat	Only mattresses
Hungary	MOHU:	Packaging Textile and mattresses Furniture
Nederlands	MRN	Only mattresses

EPR SYSTEMS in EU (furniture and mattresses)

In progress

Country	Organization	Scope
Portugal	Regulation for furniture and mattresses EPR to be set up	Furniture and mattresses
Spain	Regulation for furniture and mattresses EPR (delayed)	Furniture and mattresses
Germany	Ongoing initiative by Mattress Industry Association	Matresses
Austria	Initiative by Austria Mattress Alliance	Matresses
UK	Voluntary initiative by National Bed Federation	Matresses
Italy	Riqualta – voluntaty consortium to promote EPR for furniture	Furniture and mattresses

Potential for recycling wood through EPR - Italian figures

Furniture waste in municipal bulky waste (national projection on real data on 4 big italian urban areas)

70%

Waste stream (only municipal waste EER 20.xx.xx)	Yearly average (2021-23)	Furniture waste rate	Furniture waste (ton)
Wood	848.877	85,22%	723.452
Metals	193.789	35,43%	68.669
Plastics	61.691	28,00%	17.273
Bulky	1.051.088	68,75%	722.648
TOTAL	2.155.445	70,66%	1.532.042

Potential for recycling wood through EPR - Italian figures

Wood in furniture products (post consumer, national projection)

62%

Italian Furniture production (tons)	Wood	Metal	Plastics	Glass	Mixed materials	Stone	Total by product category	% by product category
Kitchens	191.016	11.739	2.715	175		1.088	206.733	9%
Living	108.365	38.231		7.733			154.329	6%
Bedrooms	575.992	39.409	4.250		3.950		623.601	26%
Bathroom	94.435	64.800		22.285		57.104	238.624	10%
Office	234.976	107.193	5.590				347.759	14%
Chairs	924	3.866	4.308				9.098	0%
Upholstered	125.140	80.245	3.305		52.057		260.747	11%
Mattresses	23.003	22.414	1.764		122.750		169.931	7%
Solar shades		92.451	2.886		3.266		98.603	4%
Outdoor	123.933	87.782	20.868		15.072		247.655	10%
Other metal furniture		42.453					42.453	2%
Total material	1.477.784	590.583	45.686	30.193	197.095	58.192	2.399.533	100%
%Material	62%	25%	2%	1%	8%	2%	100%	

Takeaways

1) Waste regulation on european level should actually treat wood waste as a resource

- Disparate national regulations currently cause inconsistent recycling rates. Shifting the focus toward "end-product" quality can drive innovation in sorting and cleaning technologies.
- Harmonized standards are a way, provided that the harmonization process is built around the goal of increasing recycling.

2) EPR could be enhanced to foster a larger amount of available waste to be recycled

- Furniture waste represents a significant wood waste stream that can substantially increase the availability of raw materials for recycling
- Tradeoffs to be considered – Costs are significantly higher compared to existing wood packaging recycling schemes

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